

Investigating the spatial inter-relationships of place dependency in Wales

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Summary

This paper introduces work investigating place dependency and resilience in Wales, demonstrating how towns and cities can be classified using a set of metrics on how dependent or independent they are on neighbouring places across a series of common public, commercial and social assets. The research investigates the spatial relationships of these dependencies within the context of settlement sizes, local authority types and population movement. The research has become significant over the past year with the COVID19 pandemic throwing into sharp relief the spatial inequalities in place resilience in Wales, with some places better positioned to cope with lockdowns than others, especially in the ability for people to stay local when accessing goods and services

KEYWORDS: place resilience, public assets, inter-relationships, spatial clustering, flow maps

1. Introduction

There has been a recent policy focus in the UK on towns as an important site for the delivery of local goods and services, and opportunities for employment (BIS, 2013). These characteristics make them important influences on economic performance, social cohesion and wellbeing at local and regional levels (Thurstain-Goodwin and Unwin, 2001; BIS, 2011; BIS, 2013). Where local economies are too dependent on either the public, commercial or social assets of their economy, place resilience can be vulnerable and brittle, and areas may fail to take advantage of opportunities (CLES, 2011). This research represents an initial investigation into place dependency and resilience of towns in Wales. Its aim is to develop a set of metrics which can be used to classify towns and cities based on how dependent or independent they are on other places across a series of common public, commercial and social assets and then investigate their spatial inter-relationships across Wales. The research has emerged from a wider project – Understanding Welsh Places (<http://www.understandingwelshplaces.wales/en/>) – and uses data and methods developed as part of this work. It has also been inspired by the COVID19 pandemic and the resulting restrictions on mobility which has thrown into sharp relief the spatial inequalities in place resilience in Wales, with some places better positioned to cope with lockdowns than others, especially in the ability for people to stay local when accessing goods and services.

2. Case study, data and methods

2.1 Defining Welsh places

Much of the data utilised in this analysis was compiled as part of Understanding Welsh Places (UWP), a project focused on providing data and geographical information about places in Wales for the benefit of local communities (UWP, 2021a). For this paper we use the same 193 Welsh ‘places’ defined in UWP as Contiguous Built-up Areas (CBUAs) with a resident population of 2,000 people

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or over, a cut-off chosen to make robust statistical analysis possible (UWP, 2021b). The CBUA dataset is a combination of the Office for National Statistics' (ONS') Built-up Areas and Built-up Areas with Subdivisions datasets. Using CBUAs permit the use of a wide range of government data, which can be readily assembled from small area geographies using existing lookups (Welsh Government, 2011; ONS, 2013).

2.2 Identifying relationships between Welsh places

This paper identifies the relationships between places in Wales using the Centre of Local Economic Strategies (CLES) inter-relationship model, developed as a result of their work on resilience of place (CLES, 2011; CLES, 2015). The concept of resilience, which describes how systems respond to unexpected shocks, has seen increasing application in socio-economic contexts in recent years (Singleton et. al. 2016). Recent studies have used it to better understand the impact of socio-economic change on town centres and high streets, such as the shock of the global financial crisis (Wrigley and Dolega, 2011), or the more gradual move towards online retailing (Singleton, et. al., 2016).

CLES define *place resilience* as '*the capacity of a place to be ready to deal with change and opportunity*' (CLES, 2011). Their research sought to better understand why some places are more able to respond to the challenges presented by economic, social, political or environmental shocks than others (CLES, 2011). One key finding was the importance of diversity, with places with a greater diversity of uses across the commercial, public and social sectors, proving more resilient (CLES 2011, CLES 2015).

As a result, their inter-relationship model incorporates public, commercial and social economy assets, using metrics based on nationally available data, chosen pragmatically based on the availability of consistent data (Findlay et. al. 2018) (Table 1). Aside from the travel times, each metric is divided by the residential population to give the proportion of assets relative to the population (Findlay et. al. 2018). Places are scored based on each metric, ranked accordingly, and then split into septiles (Findlay et. al. 2018). Each metric is given equal weight (Findlay et. al. 2018) and the sum of these scores creates the final total score for each place; lower total scores indicate places with a low number of assets relative to their population; a lower diversity of assets; and/or, longer travel times to services (USP, 2021; UWPb, 2021).

A key assertion of this classification is that neighbouring places are linked together (Findlay et. al. 2018), with people moving between places to take advantage of the different offering of community assets, such as opportunities for employment or recreation, or access to specific services (CLES, 2015). Places with lower total scores have a lower number of assets relative to their residential population, and are defined as 'dependent', indicating their reliance t on other neighbouring places (Findlay et. al. 2018). Places with higher total scores have a higher proportion of assets relative to their residential population and are defined as 'independent', indicating their self-sufficiency. CLES classification produces seven 'types' of place, ranging from dependent through inter-dependent to independent, with four intermediary categories included to better account for place diversity (Findlay et. al. 2018). For this paper, the nuances produced by a seven-tier classification were not required, and we have aggregated this into three types as follows: Independent (septiles 1&2), Inter-dependent (septiles 3-5) and Dependent (septiles 6&7). Figure 1 shows the distribution of Welsh places by inter-relationship category and local authority type.

Table 1: Community assets metrics used to create the CLES' inter-relationships classification

Social economy	Commercial	Public services
Number of registered charities and trustees	Number of jobs	Number of GPs and Dentists
Distance to green space	Diversity of jobs	Number of hospitals
Number of generative businesses	Public sector jobs	Number of children in primary/secondary schools
Diversity of retail offer	Number of shops	Average travel time to services
	Distance travelled to work	

Figure 1 Places with over 2000 people by inter-relationship category and local authority type.

2.3 Identifying flows between places

Modelled flows of people, known as ‘trips’, were provided by Citi Logik. These models are based on a sample of the movements of mobile devices connected to the Vodafone network, recorded between 10th May and 14th June 2015. This sample has been interpolated to represent the full UK population based on the residential population of Lower Super Output Areas (LSOAs) (Citi Logik, 2019). Trips are classified by mode of transport (approximated based on the speed of travel and the location (e.g. along a road or along a railway line)), time of day and day of the week. Here, we aggregate trips for all modes of transport for weekdays and weekends during the day (7.00 am to 6:59pm).

3. Analysis and Findings

Table 2 summarises the 193 places in Wales with a population over 2,000 people by their inter-relationship category and local authority type (urban, rural or valley). A quarter of places are largely dependent on other places for providing their goods and services, with just over half of places being inter-dependent on other places and the remaining fifth being independent settlements. Valley authorities buck this trend, having far more dependent places (nearly two-fifths) and far fewer independent places (only 4%) compared to urban and rural authorities.

Table 2 Places by inter-relationship category and local authority type

	Rural		Urban		Valley		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Independent	30	27	4	31	3	4	37	19
Inter-dependent	61	55	7	54	40	58	108	56
Dependent	20	18	2	15	26	38	48	25
Total	111	57	13	7	69	36	193	100

Table 3 and Figure 2 reveals that this is partly a reflection of the variation in settlements sizes between authorities. Valley authorities tend to have fewer very small places and more larger places, especially between 25,000-99,999 people. Moreover, small and mid-size places in the valleys (2,000-9,999 and 10,000-24,999 people respectively) tend to be more dependent or more inter-dependent on other places compared to similar places in rural authorities.

Table 3 Places by population size and local authority type

Population	Rural		Urban		Valley		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
100,000 and over			3	23			3	2
25,000 to 99,999	6	5			9	13	15	8
10,000 to 24,999	22	20	1	8	17	25	40	21
2,000 to 9,999	83	75	9	69	43	62	135	70
Total	111	100	13	100	69	100	193	100

Figure 2 Percentage of places in each inter-relationship category by settlement size and local authority type.

To understand the spatial characteristics of these inter-relationships, nearest neighbour analysis was undertaken which revealed that dependent and inter-dependent places show a degree of spatial clustering that is statistically significant at the 5% level (NNR = 0.54; z-score = -6.06 and NNR = 0.65; z-score = -6.87 respectively) but this is not the case for independent places (NNR = 1.06; z-score = 0.69). Inter-dependent places are, on average, closer to each other (5.8km) than dependent places (6.3km) and independent places (15.4km). The spatial clustering of dependent and inter-dependent places, and the short average distances between them, is expected given that they share a variety on local social economy, commercial and public service assets. To understand this spatial clustering further, Anselin Local Moran Is were calculated for the 193 places, based on their final inter-relationship score and an inverse distance decay function. Figure 3 reveals that over half of places (57%) do not display significant spatial clustering (at the 5% level), with the majority of the spatial clustering occurring in the Welsh Valleys. Here nearly all places are either categorised as being dependent places close to other dependent places (low-low cluster – 36 in all) or independent places close to dependent places (high-low cluster – 17 in all). Nearly 80% of the places in the low-low cluster had populations between 2,000-9,000 compared to only 18% for the high-low cluster, indicating that this dependency was in part a function of settlement size. Nearly half of places in the high-low cluster had populations between 25,000 and 99,0000 people.

Figure 3 Spatial clustering of inter-relationship scores (Anselin Local Moran I)

This pattern of inter-dependency is examined further by investigating flows of people between towns in the valleys using the Citi Logik data. This shows a hierarchy of flows of people between settlements of different sizes and different degrees of dependency. High-low cluster category independent towns have a larger share of people moving to towns of a similar size and of a similar dependency than smaller towns. This is illustrated in Figure 4 for week-day trips for an independent town in the middle of the Valleys. Low-low cluster category towns have a much more divergent flow of people, with flows to larger independent settlements in the Valleys as well as more local movement to similar sized settlements suggesting that small low-low cluster category towns are just dependent on each other as being dependent on more larger, independent towns.

Figure 4 Population flows from a high-low cluster town to surrounding Valley towns

4. Conclusions

This research is an initial investigation into the inter-relationships between places in Wales based on their inter-dependencies on a variety of community assets. It has identified the Welsh Valleys as a part of Wales where places are more reliant on their neighbours for supplying community assets compared to other parts of Wales. This has important implications for the resilience of these places in their ability to ride out external shocks such as the COVID19 pandemic but also economic outcomes such as those linked to Brexit. It has important implications for the demand, supply and funding of local services, particularly where people cross local authority boundaries to access them, and also policy areas such as transport planning. Future work needs to consider the importance of tuning the inter-relationships model, weighting each metric accordingly to account for different demographic characteristics and depends in a place. Finally, work needs to be undertaken on cross-border flows and the extent to which people in Wales rely on assets and services located in England. This may be the case in north east Wales where the spatial clustering of inter-relationships between places was not evident in Figure 3 despite their being a large number of dependent and inter-dependent places located here.

5. Acknowledgements

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Biographies

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